

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D3.1 Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM v1.0

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3D	Three dimensional
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
3P APP	3 rd Party Application
5G	The fifth generation of mobile technology
5GC	5G Core
5G-EIR	5G Equipment Identity Register
5G-ROUTES	5 th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials
AAS	Advanced Antenna System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
BB	Broadband
BS	Base Station
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CCDM	Cloud Core Data-Storage Manager
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
CMU	Compact Mobility Unit
CNF	Cloud Network Function
CNIS	Cloud Native Infrastructure Solution
CNIS	Cloud Native Infrastructure
CUPS	Control and User Plane Separation
E2E	End-to-end
EE	Estonia
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
EU	European Union
FI	Finland
FOC	Fiber-optical cabling
FRMCS	Future Railway Mobile Communication System

GA	Grant Agreement
gNB	g NodeB
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
HW	Hardware
IRU	Indoor Radio Unit
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LMT	Latvijas Mobilais Telefons (Latvian Mobile Telephone)
LTE	Long Term Evolution
LV	Latvia
M	Mega
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MBH	Mobile Back-Haul
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
N3IWF	Non 3GPP Interworking Function
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
NFVI	Network Functions Virtualization Infrastructure
NR	New Radio
NRF	Network Repository Function
NSA	Non-Standalone
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
O&M	Operations and Maintenance
OBU	Onboard Unit
OSS/BSS	Operations Support System/Business Support System
PaCo	Packet Core
PCF	Policy Control Function

PPS	Pulse per Second
RAN	Radio Access Network
RBS	Radio Base Station
RTT	Round Trip Time
SA	Standalone
SAT	Satellite
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMF	Session Management Function
SW	Software
TDD	Time Division Duplex
UC	Use Case
UDM	Unified Data Management
UDR	User Data Repository
UDSF	Unstructured Data Storage Function
UE	User Equipment
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VNF	Virtualized Network Function
V-RAN	Virtual Radio Access Network
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WCDMA	Wideband Code Division Multiple Access

1 Executive Summary

The objective of 5G-ROUTES project is to conduct 5th generation connected and automated mobility cross-border trials in designated 5G cross-border corridor (“Via Baltica North”). These advanced large scale field trials will take place across 3 EU member state borders (Latvia, Estonia and Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions. The aim of these tests is to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G end-to-end (E2E) interoperable CAM ecosystems and related services in digitized motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe.

The scope of deliverable 3.1 is to describe and summarize the 5G infrastructure setup for CAM in 5G-ROUTES project. This is an intermediate report that will describe the available information at the time of writing this deliverable. Described solution and information could change or can be supplemented over time and the final implemented solution will be described in the version 3.2 of this deliverable. The objective of D3.1 is to describe the 5G trial networks that will be set up by MNO’s for large scale trials in Latvia, Estonia and Finland.

It was assumed in the beginning of 5G-ROUTES project that 5G technology has been advanced further and by this time MNO’s have already commercial 5G SA core with commercial 5G SA services available in the region. By the time of writing this deliverable there is no 5G SA core available for commercial services in Latvia, Estonia or Finland. The availability of 5G SA core is essential for carrying out the large scale cross-border trials that are the objectives of 5G-ROUTES project. Situation with currently available 5G services and available frequency resources varies in Latvia, Estonia and Finland.

In this task the relevant 5G infrastructure will be installed, configured, and gradually upgraded to the latest 3GPP release. During the trials, in total 11 new 5G base stations are planned to be installed followingly:

- 2 x 5G base stations in Riga (Bikernieki racetrack) for small scale trials with virtual border crossing
- 4 x 5G base stations in Valga/Valka to cover the border crossing for trains and cars and in order to validate the use cases related to autonomous driving, infotainment services and multimodal services involving vehicles and railways
- 4 x 5G base stations in the ports of Muuga and Vuosaari + a small cell 5G base station on the ferry to cover the port areas and the ferry route in between to validate the use-cases related to multimodality, goods tracking and providing uninterrupted connectivity from Tallinn to Helsinki.

The 5G base stations for Telia network mostly on Estonia and Finland sides (except one in Riga) will be supplied, configured and upgraded by EEE and installed by TELIA, and the 5G base stations in Latvia by LMT with the support of their 5G vendor. CTTC will provide an open source 5G platform based on OpenAirInterface to be used in railways as a private 5G network. All 5G base stations will be equipped with MEC functionality, which will be managed and orchestrated by the respective MEAO from EEE. Moreover, a cloud solution and MANO stack will be deployed. The MEC nodes will be connected to each MNOs’ core network and cloud solution. The initial plan is to use also a satellite 5G connectivity via Ku-band geosynchronous and LEO satellites (OneWeb) that will be provided by ADS and which will be integrated with the MNO’s 5G CNs to support handover of PDU sessions without service disruption. This functionality is dependent on 3GPP releases and vendor support readiness in the timeframe of 5G-ROUTES project. In addition, E2E eMBB, URLLC and mMTC slices will be deployed across MNO and across satellite – terrestrial 5G domains.

The 5G infrastructure will be stand-alone and supporting 3GPP R.16. Initially there was a plan it to support also 3GPP R.17 however it is now clear that REL17 supporting network and end user devices will not be available during the project timeframe.

2 Introduction

The objective of 5G-ROUTES project is to conduct 5th generation connected and automated mobility cross-border trials in designated 5G cross-border corridor (“Via Baltica North”). These advanced large scale field trials will take place across 3 EU member state borders (Latvia, Estonia and Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions. The aim of these tests is to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and related services in digitized motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe.

The scope of deliverable 3.1 is to describe and summarize the 5G infrastructure setup for CAM in 5G-ROUTES project. This is an intermediate report that will describe the 5G trial networks that will be set up by MNO’s for large scale trials in Latvia, Estonia and Finland.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES’s Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed. The adherence to 5G-ROUTES’s GA deliverable and task descriptions can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D3.1	<i>Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM v1.0</i>	<i>Chapters 2-5</i>	<i>Chapter 2 gives a general overview of the document Chapter 3 focuses on the 5G-ROUTES rollout methodology and timeline Chapter 4 describes the setup for the trial sites of 5G-ROUTES project Chapter 5 focuses on the 5G core network solution</i>
TASKS			
<i>Task T3.1 - Installation, setup, and configuration of 5G infrastructure including seamless integration</i>	<i>Task focuses on the setup for 5G infrastructure which will be installed, configured, and gradually upgraded to the latest 3GPP release.</i>	<i>Chapter 3 Chapter 4 Chapter 5</i>	<i>Chapter 3 describes the rollout methodology including installation timeline and upgrades Chapter 4 describes the 5G trial sites with RAN setup Chapter 5 describes the core sites and setup</i>

<i>between terrestrial and satellite 5G</i>			
	<i>Task describes the installation and setup of 5G base stations for Telia and LMT.</i>	<i>Chapter 3 Chapter 4</i>	<i>Chapter 3 describes the rollout methodology, timeline, and integration/testing. Chapter 4 describes the RAN setup on each trial location, including the indoor setup, outdoor setup (including antennas), MBH setup and synchronization setup.</i>
	<i>Task describes the MEC nodes which will be connected to each MNOs' core network and cloud solution.</i>	<i>Chapter 5, S5.1.2.1</i>	<i>The MEC solution is described in S5.5</i>
	<i>Task describes the satellite 5G connectivity via Ku-band geosynchronous and LEO satellites (OneWeb) which will be integrated with the MNO's 5G CNs to support handover of PDU sessions without service disruption.</i>	<i>Chapter 4, S4.4.3.1</i>	<i>The satellite solution is described in S4.4.3.1</i>
	<i>Task describes deploying the E2E eMBB, URLLC and mMTC slices across MNO and across satellite – terrestrial 5G domains.</i>	<i>Chapter 5, S5.1.2.2</i>	<i>The slicing deployment is described in S5.1.2.2</i>

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The main purpose of the deliverable is to describe the network setup for 5G-ROUTES project trials. It covers the setup for Radio Access Network (RAN) as for the core part with its functions.

This document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 and 2 give a general overview of the document.
- Chapter 3 focuses on the 5G-ROUTES rollout methodology and timeline. It also covers the integration, testing, operation and support for the trial network.
- Chapter 4 describes the setup for the trial sites of 5G-ROUTES project. The chapter describes all the 5G RAN sites in Latvia, Estonia and Finland also covering the solutions for the ferry and train setups.
- Chapter 5 focuses on the 5G core network solution covering the aspects of vendor selection, high level network architecture, MEC solution, functionalities, and slicing.
- Chapter 6 concludes the document.

3 5G-ROUTES rollout methodology and roadmap

3.1 Rollout methodology

Rollout methodology is not fully finalized at the time of writing this report due to open questions around the 5G core solution for this project. After the 5G core solution will be finalized the needed HW for selected core and RAN solutions can be ordered. When necessary HW for the 5G core will be available implementation process can begin by the vendor. This will be followed by thorough testing process before core will be operational and ready for the trials. In parallel with last phase of 5G core implementation and testing RAN site constructions will be carried out on the selected test sites. Assuming that by the time of construction works on RAN sites are finished 5G core will be operational then RAN equipment can be integrated with the core. After initial testing, RAN sites will be operational and ready for the trials. Operational 5G-ROUTES trial network will be managed by the MNOs and the vendor in a normal operation and support cooperation. This includes among other incident and problem management, software and feature upgrades etc.

3.2 Rollout timeline

Rollout timeline depends on the vendor selections and the final 5G core solution. As at the time of writing this report the core solution is not finalized there is no detailed rollout timeline available. Ericsson has provided a rough estimation for their proposed 5G SA core solution[6]:

- Core and RAN HW ordering process – 6-8 weeks
- 5G SA core implementation – 6 months
- RAN site construction and integration – 2-3 weeks

4 5G-ROUTES trial sites setup

The 5G-ROUTES proposal states: “All use case scenarios will be incrementally validated; after the **initial in lab trials, two consecutive types of large-scale field trials will be conducted: Firstly, localized large-scale trials** at strategic locations, i.e. Valga city located on the border of Estonia and Latvia, in Tallinn and in the Gulf of Finland between Tallinn and Helsinki ports over 3GPP Release 16 (R.16) and then over R.17.” Based on this, looking for trial sites in and around the border cities of Valga (Estonia) and Valka (Latvia) was initiated by Telia and LMT as the 5G coverage providers within the consortium.

Since the automotive related use cases in the project demand a certain set of requirements (e.g. enough distance to perform lane changes or overtaking, increasing the vehicle speed beyond the limit allowed inside a city, the use of a traffic lights) to be met, some trial locations were immediately abandoned. Although there is a border crossing within the dual city of Valga/Valka, it is not possible to take the vehicles up to highway speeds (90 km/h) at or near the crossing, nor is there a possibility to use a traffic light at the same location. Hence, options for trial sites along the whole border between Estonia and Latvia were taken under consideration.

The following locations were identified and specified:

- 1) The border crossing on highway E67 at Ikla (Figure 1, point A) – this is the main gateway from Estonia to Central Europe and although there are sufficient road sections to perform even high-speed tests, it is not feasible to close the road due to the significant volume of traffic.
- 2) The border crossing on highway E77 at Murati (Figure 1, point B) – compared to the option on E67, the traffic volume through this crossing is much lower and even though Telia has a mobile site close to the crossing, it does not have a sufficient connection towards the backhaul (mobile core). LMT does not have a suitable site near this border crossing.

Figure 1 Potential automotive trial sites on the border

- 3) National highway 6 in Estonia (Figure 2) – this stretch of road heads North out of the city of Valga and runs along the Estonian-Latvian border. Considering this road, however, meant that there was no way of creating a real cross border situation since LMT nor Telia have a suitable mobile site close to this section of the highway. The deployment of a temporary site or sites next to the highway was also deliberated but it was decided not to use this option because of difficulties building a backhaul link from the site(s) and because the mast on the temporary site cannot be higher than 30 meters and thus not provide enough coverage.

Deliberating the possibility of a trial site deployment on highway 6 initiated a discussion of creating a virtual border crossing scenario if ultimately a real one cannot be created. With the virtual case, all the mobile sites are physically located on either side of the border (in Latvia or in Estonia) but are connected to different core networks – one belonging to LMT and the other to Telia. This way, if a UE in a vehicle does a handover from one site to the other, we are basically in a cross-border situation.

- 4) National highway 67 in Estonia (Figure 2) – the highway exits the city of Valga towards South-East and runs between fields and low trees. Telia has an option to use two technically suitable sites close to the considered road section but as the 3,5 GHz band is used for the trials, the sites are too far from the road – both would need to cover roughly a 4 km section of highway. LMT does not have a suitable site location close to this road section to provide coverage.

Figure 2 Potential automotive trial sites next to Valga

- 5) National road A3 in Latvia–national highway 6 in Estonia (Figure 3) – combining a section of road from both sides of the Estonian-Latvian border, a suitable area for localized large-scale trials was chosen. On the Latvian side, the road comprises of a 2 km near-straight section and an intersection (with traffic lights) which will also be used for the trials. On the Estonian side, close to the border, there is another intersection (without traffic lights) and a 0,5 km section of straight road.

LMT has a possible site location next to the road (see Section 4.2.1 for details) which enables excellent 5G coverage along the A3 road, while Telia has a site 2 km from the LMT site and 1 km from the actual border crossing.

Figure 3 Chosen trial site for automotive use cases (real cross-border scenario)

- 6) Bikernieki racetrack in Riga – before starting trials at Valga/Valka, the initial testing for some of the automotive use cases will need to be done in a highly controlled environment and a racetrack will provide this option. A virtual cross border scenario is envisaged to be demonstrated with two mobile sites – one site for LMT (Latvian) and the other for Telia (Estonian). The racetrack provides ample space to perform handovers between the “countries” and even perform high speed tests. Additionally, a temporary intersection can be built for use cases requiring its existence. The technical setup for the racetrack is further elaborated in Section 4.1.

For the use cases performed on railways, there has been only one location under consideration – the border crossing at Valga/Valka. Both LMT and Telia have the needed resources in the area and the railway itself traverses suitably between Estonia and Latvia. The mobile sites to be used for the railway use cases are detailed in Section 4.3.

As with the railway scenario, performing trials in a cross-border situation between Estonia and Finland has only entailed one possible maritime route. Although Tallinn and Helsinki are the biggest harbors in Estonia and Finland respectively, there is a drawback when it comes to the flexibility of those locations. Thus, alternative harbors, Muuga in Estonia and Vuosaari in Finland have been chosen as endpoints for the route. The technical specifications for the sites at Muuga and Vuosaari are described in Section 4.4.

Table 2 below shows how the use cases performed in 5G-ROUTES are related to different physical locations.

Table 2: 5G-ROUTES's use cases and their locations matrix

Nr	Use Case	Road Valga-Valka	Railway Valga-Valka	Muuga-Vuosaari	Bikernieki racetrack ¹
1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning				X
1.2	Cooperative lane change				X
1.3	See-Through view for safe automated overtake				X
2.1	Intersection collision control	X			
2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur	X			X
3.1	Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness	X			
3.2	Connected maintenance	X			
3.3	VRU collision avoidance	X			X
4.1	360-degree immersive multi-user gaming on the go		X		
4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the move		X		
5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics			X	
5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight		X	X	
5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation		X		

4.1 CAM sites on Bikernieki racetrack

4.1.1 Site selection and location

The Bikernieki racetrack is an international competition stage for car, motorcycle, and bicycle races. It has several configurations (see Figure 4) with minimum race width of 10 meters and maximum 16 meters perfectly suited for CAM trials. The speed lap and short oval lap are centered around start finish line, where communication tower with LMT base station is located. These laps are 3.6 and 1.7 km long trails with high speed straight and visual line of sight from the base station. Entire lap is more than 5.5 km long, nevertheless its covered in forest vegetation with limited radiofrequency penetration capacity. Finally, the shortest carting lap of 1.2 km are located just below the base station and have 8m width currently used for safe driving school.

¹ virtual cross-border trial location

Figure 4 Bikernieki racetrack lap options

Within the framework of the project, networks of two MNOs will be established at Bikernieki racetrack: Telia (Estonia) and LMT (Latvia), with the aim to simulate real conditions for cross-border trials. Virtual environment in a closed area is necessary to carry out tests under safe conditions and to enable measurements to be carried out at high vehicle speeds. Figure 5 shows a provisional plan for the test trajectory and the location of hardware deployment on the existing base station tower, which is located near the start-finish line of the track and provides direct visibility throughout the trial route. The creation of a virtual test landfill also includes several challenges that may have an impact on successful 5G network deployment for project purposes. As an example: Telia's SA Core location, where two options are under consideration, deployment at Bikernieki racetrack and in Tallinn. In the second option, it should be taken in to account that distance between racetrack and Tallinn is about 400 km and distance will give an impact to latency at least 4ms.

Figure 5 Bikernieki racetrack

4.1.2 RAN setup

The "Bikernieku trase" is a 29m communication tower which will deploy both LMT and Telia 5G antennas (Figure 6). Installation of two sectors for LMT and one sector for Telia are under consideration and preliminary installation plans are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6 "Bikernieku trase" LMT base station site - a 29m communication tower.

Figure 7 Azimuths estimation

LMT RAN vendor and the technical solution for Bikernieki test site is still to be determined and depends on the 5G core decision. More information about the core and vendor selection is described in the section 5.1.

Telia will use Ericsson Radio System on Bikernieki test site and the RAN setup consists of a Baseband 6630 unit that will be connected with the AIR 3278 via fiber optical cable as shown on the Figure 8.

Figure 8 Telia RAN setup in Bikernieki for CAM testing [4]

Baseband 6630 (Figure 9) is a powerful main digital processing unit that is part of Ericsson Radio System portfolio and is typically recommended by vendor for new installations. It supports GSM, WCDMA, LTE and NR. Advanced mixed-mode functionality allows to run several generation technologies simultaneously on one Baseband board. Baseband 6630 is a stand-alone unit that has its own integrated fan unit for climate control.

Figure 9 Ericsson Baseband 6630 [3]

Technical specifications for Baseband 6630 can be found in Annex I.

AIR 3278 (Figure 10) is a mid-band TDD Antenna Integrated Radio unit that is part of Ericsson Radio System portfolio. It is equipped with 32 transmitters and 32 receivers and the output power is 200W. It is a radio for massive MIMO that has 128 antenna elements and it is designed to operate in the 3420-3800 MHz band.

Figure 10 Ericsson AIR 3278 B78K [1]

Technical specifications for AIR 3278 B78K can be found in the Annex II.

4.2 CAM sites in Valga-Valka

Figure 11 Valka-Valga Railways and CAM use case locations

4.2.1 Site selection and location

Two junctions were selected in Valga-Valka based on existing MNO, road, and city infrastructure. Even though it would be beneficial to merge the MNO infrastructure setup for both railway and CAM use cases from cost perspective, there was no rail and road border crossing available that could be covered with one-two base stations. The railway crossing is located at one edge of the city, the road border crossing on the other. Therefore, a limited cooperation between both uses cases located on the border between Latvia and Estonia was met. Nevertheless, initial estimate indicates that almost 5 km of rails/roads will be covered with 5G connectivity by two national operators.

A detailed analysis of plausibility to deploy 5G connectivity on A3 (E264) crossing Latvia/Estonia border within bounds of twin cities Valga-Valka has been analyzed in detail. After several iterations and alternative scenarios discussed among partners a decision has been made to demonstrate 5G cross border connectivity on section Rujienas street (LV) – Viljandi street (EE) – Transpordi street (EE) and possibly on Tartu street (EE) (Figure 12). Telia has existing cellular network infrastructure (Telia VALGAVALEE) on Energia street (EE) which is right next to Transpordi street (EE). Telia active antennas are located 35m above ground level on a mast. Approximately 2km long straight section on Rujienas street (LV) has attributed LMT cellular network infrastructure (LMT Elvi). LMT active antennas are installed 41m above ground level on a platform of an industrial chimney which is large enough to add a few new antennas without problems. Initial estimates indicate that cellular network tower location in Latvia side is well suited to beam both east and west by two active MIMO antennas. On the selected route there is line of sight with the communication tower providing best network quality for the trials. Furthermore, a handover between LMT and Telia networks could be remarkably close to the physical border between both countries which is an objective for the demonstration. It should be noted that T junction on physical border of Rujienas street and Viljandi street set a limitation on car driving speed. An alternative option to increase the speed of border crossing is to explore former Customs area which currently is run by number of private businesses. Another aspect is location of traffic lights at the junction of Rujienas and Ausekla street which has an actual need for innovative solutions from municipality point of view. Within activity radius of this junction are city's hospital and shopping mall which attracts a remarkable number of pedestrians while all cross border heavy traffic is passing by.

Figure 12 Selected Valka-Valga crossing – map overview

Main advantage of selected use case location is visual line of sign throughout the whole section of the road. As shown in Figure 13 both LMT and Telia base stations could be seen at the country border junction therefore securing reliable connectivity with excellent quality.

Figure 13 Selected Valka-Valga crossing – street view

Selected Telia base station (Figure 14) is located at Energia street and is suitable to provide 5G coverage on Viljandi and Transpordi streets where CAM use cases will be tested.

Figure 14 Telia base station in Valga, Energia street

Selected LMT base station is conventionally located on the chimney as seen in Figure 15 - the base station is on the side of Rujienas street where CAM use cases are foreseen to be demonstrated. One could note that Rujienas street has two-line traffic while several junctions on that street have a third line for turning. This could be further explored for road safety and reduction of road blocking during the trials especially for platooning at above currently set speed limit within city limits.

Figure 15 Rujienas street view with LMT base station

Another advantage is existing necessity for upgrade of Rujienas street - Ausekļa street junction traffic lights from Valka city perspective. As the junction is near shopping mall, city hospital and pedestrian/bicycle road it is both heavily populated as well as critical for the first responders. One of the city's requirements is to align the junction signaling with influx of heavy traffic of goods. If smart signaling is used, both pollution from engines as well as sound pollution could be limited as traffic flow could be adjusted. This is particularly important for non-business hours when city traffic is minimal. As it could be seen in Figure 16 and Figure 17 complex signaling is used in section including separating the right turn and pedestrian crossing from overall traffic.

Figure 16 Rujienas-Ausekļa street junction – Rujienas street view

Figure 17 Rujienas-Ausekla street junction – Ausekla street view

Another advantage of the selected demonstration route is that the junction on the Estonian side (Rujienas street – Viljandi street) is equipped with closed-circuit television CCTV for local municipalities and border guards (Figure 18). An incoming video stream could be discussed with Valga city to be provided as a reference signal of upcoming traffic for Rujienas/Ausekla intersection traffic signaling. This aspect may serve as enabler for a new type of location-based service deployment integrating a virtual twin for intersections. Those location-based services could be cross checked and validated by CCTV data stream.

Figure 18 Rujienas st (LV) – Viljandi st (EE) junction equipped with municipality's CCTV's

4.2.2 RAN setup

LMT RAN vendor and the technical solution for Valga-Valka CAM test site is still to be determined and depends on the 5G core decision. More information about the core and vendor selection is described in the section 5.1.

Telia will use Ericsson Radio System on Valga-Valka test site and the RAN setup consists of a Baseband 6630 unit that will be connected with the AIR 3239 via optical cable as shown on the Figure 19.

Figure 19 Telia RAN setup in Valga for CAM testing [4]

AIR 3239 is a mid-band TDD Antenna Integrated Radio unit that is part of Ericsson Radio System portfolio. It is equipped with 32 transmitters and 32 receivers that improves LTE TDD spectral efficiency. The output power is 200W. It is a radio for massive MIMO and it is designed to operate in the 3420-3600MHz band.

Technical specifications for AIR 3239 B78F can be found in the Annex III.

Telia will use the same Baseband 6630 in Valga site for CAM trails as in Bikernieki racetrack. More detailed information about Baseband 6630 is described in the section 4.1.2.

4.3 Railway sites in Valga-Valka

4.3.1 Selection of sites

As mentioned in the beginning of Chapter 4, there has only been one possible location for performing the trials associated with railways. As seen on Figure 20, the railway section, which crosses the Estonian-Latvian border, between the stations of Valga and Lugaži will be used. There are 3 possible mobile sites along the mentioned railway corridor which will be discussed below – two from Telia and one from LMT.

Figure 20 Location for the railway use cases – Valga-Lugaži connection

For LMT, the ValkaLTK tower (see Figure 20) is used to provide 5G coverage. The tower itself is 62m tall and stands on high ground in relation to the railway line. A MIMO antenna (1 sector) will be installed to the tower and directed towards the Lugaži train station. Figure 21, photographed at the antenna height, illustrates that from the site, the railway line is clearly visible, however there is a risk of no direct line of site to the Lugaži station due to vegetation. Stemming from this, trials performed during spring or winter will greatly increase the chances of obtaining a higher quality 5G signal on the railway.

Figure 21 Birds eye view from ValkaLTK site at antenna height – direction towards Lugaži station

Telia has two sites for covering the railway corridor with 5G coverage (see Figure 20). Based on the discussion with use case leaders only the VALGAVALVT site will be used for the trials as the train station itself does not necessarily need to have 5G coverage. The used VALGAVALVT site will be deployed on top of a 30m high tower and will have 2 sectors – both directed along the railway in opposite directions.

4.3.2 RAN setup for the sites

LMT RAN vendor and the technical solution for Valga-Valka railway use case test site is still to be determined and depends on the 5G core decision. More information about the core and vendor selection is described in the section 5.1.

Telia will use the same Baseband 6630 and AIR 3239 RAN site setup in Valga site for railway use cases as in Telia Valga site for CAM use cases. More detailed information about Telia Valga site for CAM use cases is described in the section 4.2.2.

4.3.3 Technical setup for the train

As many trials are performed inside the train, 5G coverage with sufficient signal quality is needed there. To achieve this, different options were considered:

- 1) using coverage from the VALKALTK and VALGAVALVT sites – no additional technical solution inside the train will be deployed to boost 5G signal quality.
- 2) using coverage from the VALKALTK and VALGAVALVT sites with an active repeater inside the train to boost 5G signal quality.
- 3) relaying the 5G signal into the train using a passive system where an external antenna is connected to an internal antenna.

Out of the listed options, the first one was chosen - to use coverage from the mobile sites with no additional setup inside the train. This decision is largely based on previous experience of the MNOs regarding 5G signal propagation but also considers the type of train to be used for the trials (a Soviet train with weak shielding in windows and walls) and the fact that attaching external hardware (HW) on trains is a complicated procedure and requires the HW to be certified. It must be noted however that the chosen approach will ultimately be validated after the initial tests when the actual 5G signal quality inside the train will be measured.

4.4 Maritime sites

4.4.1 Site selection and location

The 5G-ROUTES project is addressing new connectivity challenges of covering a ~80km ferry route with 5G network. Between Estonia and Finland there are several possible ferry routes to consider for the trials. In the Tallinn-Helsinki route there are two main options:

- a) From Tallinn city center to Helsinki city center;
- b) From Muuga port (located in the edge of Tallinn) to Vuosaari port (located in the edge of Helsinki).

As option B is one of the main cargo routes between Estonia and Finland, it has better infrastructure in the ports for building mobile network and the port of Muuga will be the main hub after Rail Baltica project has been finished, we have chosen the option for 5G-ROUTES trials.

The selected ferry route and the ferry which will be used for the use-cases can be seen on Figure 22.

Figure 22 Muuga-Vuosaari ferry route and Eckerö Finbo vessel [7]

In the Muuga port side the 5G base station will be located on a 100m building (site name HARJUMUUSA) as seen on Figure 23.

Figure 23 Telia EE site in Muuga harbor on top of an elevator building

It is the highest building/ object in the area and will enable providing the needed mobile network coverage to at least half of the bay with 700MHz, but also cover the port area with 3,5GHz frequency radios.

On the Vuosaari side the site for the 5G base stations has not yet been selected.

4.4.2 RAN setup

Identical Ericsson Radio System equipment and RAN site setup will be used on Muuga and Vuosaari harbors. Both sites will have two 3,5GHz sectors that are used to create 5G coverage on the harbor area and one 700MHz sector is used to cover the shipping route over the Gulf of Finland. RAN setup (Figure 24) consists of a Baseband 6630 that will be connected with the AIR 3239 and the radio 2460 via fiber optical cables. More detailed information about Baseband 6630 is described in the section 4.1.2 and more information about AIR 3239 can be found in the section 4.2.2. The antenna setup is not finalized and depends on the coordination with site owners and the possibilities to mount additional antennas. Initial plan is to use 4-port antenna KRE 101 2412/1 that will be connected to the radio 2460.

Technical specifications for KRE 101 2412/1 can be found in the Annex IV.

Figure 24 Telia RAN site setup in Muuga and Vuosaari [4]

4.4.3 Ferry setup

Shipping companies are interested of providing their passengers with on-board connectivity on their vessels, because nowadays this is a very important part of the travelling experience. Due to maritime specificity – long distances over the seas and usually large vessels – this is always not an easy task. First challenge is providing the connectivity to the moving vessel and the next challenge is to provide connectivity on the vessel itself due to typical maritime vessel construction and size specificity. These challenges create limitations for the connection

quality and coverage which is usually the reasoning why connectivity is provided only on a certain passenger decks and areas on the vessels.

The 5G-ROUTES project is collaborating with Eckerö Line and will use their vessel Finbo to enhance the connectivity to and on the vessel using 5G. Currently the vessel has 1Gbit radio-link connection to the shore that is used to provide Wi-Fi connection on passenger decks. The aim is to enhance the connectivity for the passenger and also car decks with 5G. In addition to RAN setup on the both sides of the shores (described in section 4.4.2) a 5G base station will be built on the vessel to provide 5G on-board connectivity. Utilizing SAT connection and 5G core transmission for load balancing will ensure continuous backhaul connectivity to this 5G base station throughout the voyage.

The on-board RAN setup (Figure 25) will include advanced antenna system (AAS) that will be connected to the ERS Baseband. The ERS Baseband will be connected to the indoor radio unit (IRU) with fibre optical cable and the IRU is further connected with two radio DOTs with Cat 6 cables. Connection between the core and ERS Baseband will be established via existing radio-link. The on-board solution also includes GPS for synchronization. The ERS Baseband and IRU will be installed to the ferry server room and indoor DOT will be installed one deck lower to the passenger area. GPS, AAS and satellite antennas will be installed outside the ferry on deck 9. For the satellite connection Airbus will provide backbone connectivity satellite radio and antenna (from TBD satellite service provider) that is connected to the base station particularly for serving IoT messaging throughout the journey. More detailed overview of the CAM infrastructure setup in maritime will be covered in the deliverable 3.3 of 5G-ROUTES project.

Figure 25 RAN architecture on ferry [4]

4.4.3.1 SAT solution

SAT solution is not finalized at the moment of writing this report and is highly dependent on the 5G core solution that will be used in 5G-ROUTES project. More information and progress about the 5G core used in this project can be found from chapter 5. Initial schematics about the SAT solution that are considered to be implemented on the ferry can be seen on Figure 26. More information about the satellite 5G connectivity can be found from deliverable 1.3 section 6.7 and information about satellite communication networks in general is described in

deliverable 1.1 section 2.3 and specifically on the set-up on the ferry is briefly presented in deliverable 3.3 section 7.1.

Use N3IWF for “legacy” Satellite Radio Access Network

Figure 26 N3IWF usage for Satellite RAN [5]

4.5 Spectrum regulation and availability

Detailed overview of the spectrum regulation and availability in Latvia, Estonia and Finland is described in deliverable D1.3 in section 5.1. In the following chapter a short summary of the spectrum regulation and availability for 5G-ROUTES trial locations is described.

4.5.1 Spectrum availability in Latvia – Valka and Bikernieki

In Latvia 5G network development is carried out at 3.5 GHz frequency, which is divided into 50MHz frequency blocks and available to three MNOs. To provide seamless 5G coverage, 3.5 GHz spectrum, owned by LMT, will be used for the network deployment in test sites located in Latvia. LMT owns two 50 MHz frequency blocks – 3400-3450 MHz and 3650-3700 MHz. In Bikernieki trial site the lower frequency block will be used for LMT, but with a distinction that the block from 3400 MHz to 3410 MHz cannot be used to provide live services to their customers. This is a reason why LMT will provide 5G coverage only in 40 MHz block in Bikernieki. Telia will have 50 MHz block at their disposal from 3650 MHz to 3700 MHz which will be provided on the basis of temporary frequency license awarded by the Latvian national regulator (Electronic Communications Office).

4.5.2 Spectrum availability in Estonia – Valga and Muuga

In Estonia the 3.5 GHz auction was suspended in April 2019 and thus Telia do not own a 3.5GHz spectrum license at the current moment. The auction can resume in 2021, however since ending the court case in Q2 2020 it has been postponed bi-monthly. The current due date for registering to the auction is in August 2021, but we have to keep in mind the ongoing progress to change the current auction rules and the network security act (aka “The Huawei law”) which has communicated as a prerequisite for holding any 5G related frequency auctions. So the auction date can easily be postponed to the coming years. In 5G-ROUTES project scope Telia Estonia have few possible scenarios regarding bands and spectrum used in Valga and Muuga trial locations:

- Trial licenses for 700 MHz and 3.5 GHz bands;
- Usage of existing bands;
- Commercially available spectrum if auction will be carried out.

4.5.3 Spectrum availability in Finland – Vuosaari

700 MHz band in Finland was assigned in November 2016, which is paired frequency band: 703 – 733 MHz and 758 - 788 MHz. Band is divided by three MNOs where 10 MHz in lower part and 10 MHz in upper part are available for each of them. Telia Finland has two 10 MHz frequency blocks – 723-733 MHz and 778-788 MHz that can be used to cover the ferry route over the Gulf of Finland.

The entire 3.5 GHz band was auctioned in September 2018 for the construction of nationwide wireless broadband, with a total of 390 MHz available to three MNOs. Telia Finland owns 130 MHz out of the total bandwidth available in the 3.5 GHz band – 3410-3480 MHz and 3600-3660 MHz² that can be used to create 5G coverage in the Vuosaari harbor area.

4.6 MBH and transmission setup

The general purpose of mobile backhaul and the transmission network is to connect mobile base station nodes with a core network as seen on Figure 27.

Figure 27 High level MBH solution for an MNO [8]

The final MBH and transmission setup on both MNO sides is currently still to be determined and is highly dependent on the 5G core solutions and the locations.

The solution for each location differs and depends on MBH options available on the base station site and the core part where the connection ends. The MBH starting from the base station sites on the 5G-ROUTES project is currently planned as seen on

² Nationwide, excluding the province of Åland, where Telia Finland owns 100 MHz frequency block in the 3.5 GHz band – 3410-3510 MHz

Table 3.

Table 3: MBH solution on 5G-ROUTES gNB sites

gNB site	MBH medium	Bandwidth
Bikernieki (Riga)	Radio link	N/A
ValkaLTK (Valka)	N/A	N/A
ValkaELVI (Valka)	N/A	N/A
ValgaVALEE(Valga)	FOC	1Gbps
ValgaVALVT (Valga)	FOC	1Gbps
Muuga	FOC	1Gbps
Vuosaari	FOC	1Gbps
Eckerö ferry	Radio link	1Gbps
	SAT connectivity	1Mbps

4.7 Synchronization setup

5G has more strict requirements regards to synchronization than the older mobile generations. Especially important is it for TDD (Time Division Duplex) which is used in frequency band n78 and for mmWave applications. The requirement for synchronization accuracy (TimeError between two gNBs) is following:

- $\pm 1.5 \mu\text{s}$ for basic (TDD) services, leaving $\pm 1.1 \mu\text{s}$ for transport;
- $\pm 10 \text{ ns}$ for positioning services.

In 5G-ROUTES project the required synchronization accuracy is acquired with GPS, which distributes accurate time information and can be used as a clock source for the RBS Uu interface. An RBS that uses GPS as a clock source for the Uu interface must be equipped with a GPS receiver that is connected to an antenna with direct visibility from GPS satellites as shown in Figure 28.

The GPS receiver can provide the following types of information for Uu interface synchronization:

- A 1-Pulse-per-Second (1PPS) signal for frequency synchronization of the system clock and carrier frequency synchronization of the Uu interface
- Absolute time for time and phase synchronization of the Uu interface
- The GPS receiver must be an Ericsson GPS receiver

Figure 28 RBS Connectivity to GPS [4]

5 5G Core

In the heart of every mobile network is the core. Its tasks include authentication and authorization of the users, session and slice management, mobility management and security, just to name a few. In essence, without the core there is no network. The following sections discuss the 5G core for the 5G-ROUTES and elaborate on its current state at month 9 of the project.

5.1 Vendor selection

From the project standpoint, the use of operational 5G networks of LMT and Telia was planned for the trials. At the time of writing however, it is clear, that this will not be possible due to various reasons, of which the main are:

- Regulatory issues – national regulators in Latvia and Estonia have not allotted commercially usable spectrum for 5G or have done so with specific distinctions which have hindered the deployment of 5G networks.
Spectrum for commercial use is available only for Telia FI.
- Company policies – LMT and Telia are both subsidiaries of multinational companies in which different policies dictate how and when new technologies are deployed in which country. Keeping in mind that Latvia and Estonia are small markets, commercial 5G deployments in these countries will take its time.
- Commercial availability of network functions – for both core network vendors Nokia and Ericsson the commercial SA functions currently available are very limited and would highly restrict the trialing of use-cases. Also it is not seen on the roadmaps that all the needed functionalities would be commercially available during the project time.

With no operational 5G cores available initially for 5G-ROUTES, the project partners have been looking at possibilities to acquire these. Based on the requirements of the use cases, an SA solution has been in the focus of the acquisition process with Nokia and Ericsson as possible vendors. Telia has also been looking from within the Telia Group, however no country in the group currently operates a 5G core capable enough to fulfill the needs of the project.

The main requirements for the core(s) include:

- a compact central control plane (a container solution if possible).
- slicing capability (at least three slices).
- the possibility of deploying a UPF.
- the possibility of deploying an LMF.
- URLLC capability.
- eMBB capability.
- MEC deployment.
- MANO deployment.

At M09 of the 5G-ROUTES project, the MNOs have the following overall results from the researched options:

- Ericsson Innovation Lab – using the lab in Kista, Sweden has been deemed not possible due to functionality issues.
- Telia Group – the only subsidiary from the Telia Group with minor 5G SA capability is currently Telia FI and although they have a container solution available, it is in a very immature state and is in the initial trial phase with limited functionality.
- Ericsson’s proposed solution – the proposal has been analyzed and some decisions are pending both for LMT and Telia.

- Nokia's proposed Solution – the proposal has been analyzed and some decisions are pending both for LMT and Telia.
- Chinese vendors – no attempts were made to pursue this line due to the global political situation towards Chinese vendors.

The following sections describe Ericsson's and Nokia's offer in more detail and presents the decisions made thus far. It must be noted however, that the content of both offers is confidential and cannot be disclosed to anyone other than the companies who requested them (MNOs).

5.1.1 Nokia's core solution

LMT has long-term cooperation with Nokia and uses their systems for 2G, 3G and 4G networks while Telia has just recently migrated its 2G, 3G and 4G networks to a core provided by Nokia. For 5G-ROUTES, both LMT and Telia focused on assessing the different technical capabilities offered, to ensure the best possible results within the project. Also, during the evaluation phase, the sustainability of the cores was taken into consideration with a view to exploit them for commercial use after the project ends. The possibility of using multi-vendor RAN and SA core was also assessed, but it must be noted that this was seen as a complicating factor for the project's execution due to a high probability of compatibility issues.

The offers made by Nokia to LMT and Telia were similar (not identical due to the different historical background of the MNOs) and on a high level included the following options:

- 1) **standard deployment** – option 1 to satisfy the needs of the project. The solution has been diluted when it comes to full 5G SA functionality but in essence, this is a commercial solution which:
 - a. is scalable during the project and after it ends.
 - b. is future proof for the MNOs.
 - c. requires NFVI readiness.
 - d. requires a significant amount of space in a datacenter.
 - e. has no redundancy.
- 2) **Compact Mobility Unit (CMU)** – option 2 for the project. In essence, this is a “core-in-a-box” solution, designed originally for private networks but envisaged to fulfill the needs of smaller projects as well. The solution:
 - a. has all the hardware in one container.
 - b. has a minimal version of a commercial software.
 - c. has no inbound roaming.
 - d. has a new SW release available depending on the SW availability for large systems and with a 3-month delay added.
 - e. cannot be used after the project.
 - f. is capably of only manual slice design and creation.
 - g. is designed in a way where an additional CMU with only a UPF installed will be deployed on the edge sites.
 - h. has redundancy.

5.1.2 Ericsson's core solution

Both LMT and Telia have also historically been involved with Ericsson, as with Nokia, and thus the offers made by Ericsson to the MNOs were again quite similar. An outtake from the offer to Telia is seen on Figure 29 in the form of a high-level core solution. Similar to what Nokia offered, the solution contains a central core site (in a datacenter) and a possibility to deploy an edge site with a UPF closer to the end user.

Ericsson's solution:

- a. has a single platform for EPC and 5GC functionalities.
- b. has a cloud native/microservice architecture.
- c. has a high user plane scalability.
- d. has network exposure capabilities for programmability, meaning there is an option to control, for instance, slice management through enablers created within the project.
- e. flexible allocation and control of network resources.
- f. is not future proof for the MNOs.
- g. has roaming capabilities.
- h. requires a significant amount of space in the datacenter.
- i. does not require NFVI for the project.

Figure 29 Core deployment options for Ericsson's solution [6]

The low-level view of the core on Figure 30 illustrates the different functions in the service-based architecture (SBA). The existence of many of the functions depends on the use cases performed in the network, however some are nearly always present:

- a. AMF – the access and mobility management function deals with the sessions (connection and mobility management tasks) for the UE and communicated with the SMF regarding session management.
- b. SMF – the session management function is a fundamental element in the SBA responsible for interacting with the decoupled data plane and managing session context with the UPF.
- c. UPF – the user plane function is an evolution of the control and user plane separation (CUPS) strategy which allows data packet processing and traffic aggregation to be performed closer to the network edge. In essence, it is the contact point between the mobile infrastructure and an external data network.
- d. UDM – the unified data repository is, as the name suggests, a database which stores and manages different subscription-based information.
- e. AUSF – the authentication server function manages the authentication of the 5G UEs.
- f. PCF – the policy control function provides policy rules to be enforced for the control plane function.
- g. NSSF – the network slice selection function manages the selection of the optimal network slice available for the service, requested by the user.

- h. LMF – although not present in Figure , the location management function has also been requested by the project members from the potential core vendors. The LMF is a central concept in the 5G positioning architecture which manages the support of different location-based services for the UE.

Figure 30 5G SA core low level view [6]

5.1.2.1 MEC solution

MEC is a functionality needed for certain use cases in 5G-ROUTES, such as UC 4.2, where computational power is required close to the end user. Figure 31 illustrates the approach taken by Ericsson in their offer. It must be noted that the direction taken by Nokia in their proposal, on a high level, was similar.

Figure 31 MEC architecture [6]

The complete solution proposed has been optimized for 5G use cases with high throughput or low round trip time (RTT) requirements with local breakouts for selected devices, services or IP flows. All-in-all, virtual network functions (VNF) and edge applications can be run on the same platform. Additionally, VNFs, applications, and infrastructure can be managed from a centralized single pane of glass. As seen on the figure, the central site houses the 5G packet core (PaCo) while the UPF has been deployed at the edge. The full core solution enables the 3rd party applications to be deployed at each physical site if needed.

5.1.2.2 Slicing

The proposed slicing capability in the offer is illustrated in Figure 32 and Figure 33. Again, a similar approach from Ericsson and Nokia can clearly be identified. Figure reveals the NFs which enable a specific slice and how these are interconnected. The solution allows for some of the NFs to be used for multiple slices.

Figure 32 5G Network Slicing Architecture [6]

Figure 33 illustrates the multitude of UCs which can harness its own slice. For 5G-ROUTES, a maximum of three slices is planned: eMBB, URLLC and IoT. The same figure also points to a crucial entity in the solution which is orchestration. This enables, among other tasks, the flexible management of slices.

Based on the information regarding functionality, provided by Nokia and Ericsson, and considering the financial aspects, Telia EE has made a decision to proceed in the project with a 5G SA core from Ericsson. The CMU solution proposed by Nokia, was, from a functional standpoint, not satisfactory, e.g. the lack of roaming capabilities will virtually make it impossible to perform the tests needed in specific use cases. As for Nokia’s standard deployment, integrating it into Telia’s existing infrastructure (including NFVI) turned out to be extremely challenging and resource heavy for a project this size. The decision was further reinforced by the fact that Ericsson beat Nokia with a clear margin price wise.

For LMT, the decision regarding the core, is still pending and will most likely not be taken before M10 of the project.

Figure 33 Examples of Network Slicing used for different services [6]

As a final note regarding the 5G core (and the technical setup in general), the authors of D3.1 wish to emphasize that most of the decisions have not yet been done for reasons discussed earlier in the document. As the core is the central entity in the 5G network, the whole architectural solution will grow out of it. For example, the physical configuration of the core will determine where it will be deployed (MNOs’ main datacenters or somewhere else), which in turn will determine how the backhaul connections for the RAN part will be built (keeping in mind the trial sites) and where to deploy the MEC nodes, based on technical feasibility etc. Stemming from this, D3.1 still has many gaps in content and will be expanded significantly in D3.2.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable gives an overview of the planned and existing infrastructure and selected trial locations for 5G-ROUTES project in Latvia, Estonia and Finland. At the time of writing this deliverable several key areas of the infrastructure setup for 5G-ROUTES project are still to be determined and thus the trial network setup is not fully finalized. This document is the initial version of the infrastructure setup for CAM and the final implemented solution will be described in the version 3.2 of this deliverable. In the beginning of this project it was assumed that 5G technology have advanced further by this time and MNOs in the region will have commercial 5G SA core with commercial services available, but at the current moment there is no 5G SA core available for commercial services in Latvia, Estonia or Finland. The availability of 5G SA core is essential for carrying out the large scale cross-border trials that are the objectives of 5G-ROUTES project and thus MNOs together with the project partners are currently looking for possible solutions. The infrastructure deployment schedule is dependent on the final decision on the 5G core solution and vendor selection. In the following 6-month period next steps will be:

- 5G core solution finalization by the MNOs
- Architecture of the trial networks
- 5G core HW ordering and implementation
- RAN HW ordering, construction and integration

7 References

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Annex I: Technical specifications for Baseband 6630 with fan

MECHANICAL SPECIFICATIONS	Product dimensions	44 mm (Product Height) 483 mm (Product Width) 383 mm (Product Depth)
	Product weight	6420 g
	Cooling method	Self Contained
	Height in rack units	1 (Product Height in U)
	Mounting options	19" rack
CERTIFICATIONS	Encapsulation class	IP20
	Safety standards	IEC/EN 62 368-1 UL 62 368-1 IEC/EN 60 529-1
	Regulatory approval	CE CB
	NEBS compliance	GR-63 GR-1089 GR-3108
	EMC immunity	ETSI EN 301 489-1 TS37.113
	EMC emission	ETSI EN 301 489-1 ETSI EN 301 489-50 ETSI EN 301 908-1 FCC Part 15 ICES-003 TS37.113
	EMC Emission class	Class B
ENVIRONMENTAL SPECIFICATIONS	Normal operation temperature	0 °C (Min Temperature) 55 °C (Max Temperature)
ELECTRICAL SPECIFICATIONS	Typical power consumption	118 W
1 GBPS ETHERNET ELECTRICAL PORT	Connector application	Ethernet-1G Ethernet-10G
	Number of ports	2
	Port type	SFP+
BASEBAND TO BASEBAND DATA LINK PORT	Connector application	IDLe
	Number of ports	2
	Port type	XCede
RADIO INTERFACE CPRI PORT	Number of ports	9
	Port type	SFP+
	Connector application	CPRI-2.4G CPRI-4.9G CPRI-9.8G CPRI-10.1G
RADIO INTERFACE CPRI/ECPRI PORT	Connector application	CPRI-2.4G CPRI-4.9G CPRI-9.8G CPRI-10.1G eCPRI-10.3G

	Number of ports	6
	Port type	SFP+
GNSS RECEIVER SYNCHRONIZATION	Number of ports	1
	Port type	RJ45
	Connector application	GPS
SUPPORT ALARM UNIT PORT	Connector application	ECB Protected with Power
	Number of ports	1
	Port type	10-pin modular
LOCAL MANAGEMENT PORT	Connector application	Local Maintenance Terminal (LMT)
	Number of ports	1
	Port type	RJ45
ENCLOSURE CONTROL BUS PORT	Connector application	ECB Regular
	Number of ports	1
	Port type	RJ45
PORT EXTERNAL ALARM	Number of ports	2
	Connector application	External Alarm (EA)
	Port type	RJ45
PORT -48V DC POWER	Port type	Power Connector
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION	Application	General
	Radio standard	Multi std

Annex II: Technical specifications for AIR 3278 B78K

RADIO GENERAL	Massive MIMO Segment	Compact
RADIO CHARACTERISTICS	Cascading support	Not Applicable (Boolean)
RF GROUP	Maximum AAS UL Operational BW	200 MHz
	Maximum AAS DL Operational BW	200 MHz
ENVIRONMENTAL SPECIFICATIONS	Normal operation temperature	-40 °C (Min Temperature) 55 °C (Max Temperature)
	Normal Operation Relative Humidity	2% (Min Relative Humidity) 100% (Max Relative Humidity)
MECHANICAL SPECIFICATIONS	Board Restore Button	No
	Product dimensions	621 mm (Product Height) 371 mm (Product Width) 185 mm (Product Depth)
	Product weight	25000 g
	Maintenance button	No
	Product volume	42.2 l
	Product environment	Outdoor
	Cooling method	Natural Convection
	Fan option	No
	Mounting options	Wall Pole/Mast
	Mounting direction	Primary Vertical
CERTIFICATIONS	Radio Standards - International	3GPP TS38.141-1 3GPP TS38.141-2
	Encapsulation class	IP65
	Safety standards	IEC/EN 60 950-22 IEC/EN 62 368-1
	Regulatory approval	CE
	NEBS compliance	N/A
	EMC immunity	3GPP TS 38.113
	EMC emission	3GPP TS 38.113

	EMC Emission class	Class B
	EU Directives	RoHS2 2011/65/EU RED 2014/53/EU
	EMF Standards	EN/IEC 62232
CPRI	Supported boot line rates	10.3 Gbit/s
	Supported operating line rates	10.3 Gbit/s 25.8 Gbit/s
PORT -48V DC POWER	Port type	Power Connector
PORT GROUNDING	Port type	2 x M6 bolt
	Number of ports	1
PORT EXTERNAL ALARM/EC LIGHT	Connector application	EC Light External Alarm (EA)
PORT DATA	Number of ports	2
	Connector application	eCPRI-10.3G eCPRI-25.8G
	Port type	SFP28
PORT RF	Connector application	Output monitor
RADIO INFORMATION	Operating band	Band 78K (3500 MHz)
	NR operation	supported
	Supported operation modes (DL, singleband)	Band B78K: NR (SRO)
	NB IoT support	not supported
	Beam RAT Support	Beam ID BrM1, BrHS1, Tr1, Tr2: Band B78K / NR / Supported

Annex III: Technical specifications for AIR 3239 B78F

RADIO GENERAL	Massive MIMO Segment	Compact
	Radio type	AIR 3239 (Type of Radio Units)
RF GROUP	Maximum AAS UL Operational BW	100 MHz
	Maximum AAS DL Operational BW	100 MHz
ENVIRONMENTAL SPECIFICATIONS	Normal operation temperature	-40 °C (Min Temperature) 55 °C (Max Temperature)
	Normal Operation Relative Humidity	5% (Min Relative Humidity) 100% (Max Relative Humidity)
	Wind Speed	67mm/sec
MECHANICAL SPECIFICATIONS	Product dimensions	530 mm (Product Height) 411 mm (Product Width) 136 mm (Product Depth)
	Product weight	24000 g
	Maintenance button	No
	Product volume	29 l
	Product environment	Outdoor
	Mounting options	Wall Pole/Mast
	Mounting direction	Primary Vertical
CERTIFICATIONS	Encapsulation class	IP65
ECPRI	Supported operating line rates	10.3 Gbit/s 25.8 Gbit/s
PORT -48V DC POWER	Power supply	-48V
PORT EXTERNAL ALARM/EC LIGHT	External alarm/EC light connector type	DIN 14 female connector
PORT TX MONITOR	TX monitor port connector type	SMA female connector
DATA 1 CONNECTOR OPTICAL	Data 1 optical connector type	LC/PC
AUX CONNECTOR OPTICAL	AUX optical connector type	LC/PC
RADIO INFORMATION	Operating band	Band 78F (3500 MHz)
	NR operation	supported
	Supported operation modes (DL, singleband)	Band B78F: NR (SRO)

	NB IoT support	not supported
	Beam RAT Support	Beam ID BrHS1, BrHS2, BrM1, BrM2, Tr1, Tr2: Band B78F / NR / Supported Beam ID BrHS1, BrHS2, BrM1, BrM2, Tr1, Tr2: Band B78F / LTE TDD / HW prepared

Annex IV: Technical specifications for 4-Port Antenna KRE 101 2412/1

Type No.		KRE 101 2412/1			
Left side, lowband		R1, connector 1-2			
698-960					
Frequency Range	MHz	698 – 807	791 – 862	824 – 894	880 – 960
Gain at mid Tilt	dBi	15.9	16.5	16.6	17.1
Gain over all Tilts	dBi	15.9 ± 0.8	16.5 ± 0.5	16.6 ± 0.5	17.0 ± 0.7
Horizontal Pattern:					
Azimuth Beamwidth	°	67 ± 3.3	63 ± 3.0	62 ± 4.1	60 ± 3.4
Front-to-Back Ratio, Total Power, ± 30°	dB	> 23	> 24	> 23	> 24
Vertical Pattern:					
Elevation Beamwidth	°	9.2 ± 0.8	8.3 ± 0.4	8.0 ± 0.3	7.5 ± 0.5
Electrical Downtilt continuously adjustable	°	0.0 – 10.0			
Tilt Accuracy	°	< 1.2	< 1.3	< 1.2	< 1.3
First Upper Side Lobe Suppression	dB	> 15	> 16	> 16	> 16
Cross Polar Isolation	dB	> 27			
Port to Port Isolation	dB	>27 (R1 // R2)			
Max. Effective Power per Port	W	300 (at 50 °C ambient temperature)			

Right side, lowband		R2, connector 3-4			
698-960					
Frequency Range	MHz	698 – 807	791 – 862	824 – 894	880 – 960
Gain at mid Tilt	dBi	16.0	16.5	16.6	17.0
Gain over all Tilts	dBi	15.9 ± 0.8	16.5 ± 0.5	16.6 ± 0.5	17.0 ± 0.7
Horizontal Pattern:					
Azimuth Beamwidth	°	68 ± 4.0	63 ± 3.1	62 ± 4.4	60 ± 4.0
Front-to-Back Ratio, Total Power, ± 30°	dB	> 23	> 23	> 24	> 25
Vertical Pattern:					
Elevation Beamwidth	°	9.1 ± 0.8	8.2 ± 0.4	8.0 ± 0.3	7.5 ± 0.5
Electrical Downtilt continuously adjustable	°	0.0 – 10.0			
Tilt Accuracy	°	< 1.1	< 1.2	< 1.2	< 1.3
First Upper Side Lobe Suppression	dB	> 15	> 15	> 15	> 15
Cross Polar Isolation	dB	> 27			
Port to Port Isolation	dB	>27 (R2 // R1)			
Max. Effective Power per Port	W	300 (at 50 °C ambient temperature)			

Electrical specifications, all ports		
Impedance	Ω	50
VSWR		< 1.5
Return Loss	dB	> 14
Interband Isolation	dB	> 27
Passive Intermodulation	dBc	< -153 (2 x 43 dBm carrier)
Polarization	°	-45, +45
Max. Effective Power for the Antenna	W	800 (at 50 °C ambient temperature)

Mechanical specifications		
Input		4 x 4.3-10 female
Connector Position		bottom
Adjustment Mechanism		Integrated RET, continuously adjustable
Wind load (at Rated Wind Speed: 150 km/h)	N lbf	Frontal: 1450 326 Maximal: 1590 357
Max. Wind Velocity	km/h mph	200 124
Height / Width / Depth	mm inches	2500 / 445 / 130 98.4 / 17.5 / 5.1
Weight	kg lb	28.2 / 36.2 (clamps incl.) 62.2 / 79.8 (clamps incl.)
Packing Size	mm inches	2845 / 550 / 205 112.0 / 21.7 / 8.1
Scope of Supply		Antenna, mounting kit incl. mech. Tilt-kit 0° to 10° tilt, integrated RET

Annex V: Technical specifications for Ericsson radio 2460

Bands	Supported Standards			Output Power (W)					Planned Certification	Note
	Bx	By	BZ	Bx	By	Bz	Total without fan	Total with fan		
Radio 2460 24B8 24B20 24B28B C	GWLN	LN	LN	2x80	2x40	2x40	2x160	2x160	CE	Available as /1.

Radio 2460/2479	Dimension (mm)	Notes
without protruding & wo. Fan	478H x 384W x 183D (~33,6 liter)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> H (Handle, connectors and protruding are excluded) W (Protruding for rail mounting is excluded) D (Distance plug and higher fin/wall are excluded)
w. protruding but wo. Fan	555H x 397.5W x 190D	
wo. protruding but w. Fan	478H x 384W x 183D (~33,6 liter)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> H (Handle, connectors and protruding are excluded) W (Protruding for rail mounting is excluded) D (Distance plug is excluded)
w. protruding & Fan	555H x 397.5W x 190D	

Unit type	Weight	Note
Radio 2460	37.1 kg	Without optional fan
Fan unit	1.9 kg	